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Abstracts

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FunGlass

HIGH TEMPERATURE OXIDATION BEHAVIOUR OF PASSIVE FILLER LOADED POLYSILAZANE-DERIVED GLASS/CERAMIC COATING SYSTEMS ON AISI 441 STAINLESS STEEL

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Abstract

The objective of this work is to design a composite coating system, which has better performance in respect of lifetime compared to stainless steel. For that purpose, polymer derived ceramic (PDC) coating systems consisting of a bond coat applied by dip coating and a top coat deposited by spray coating technique were developed. The pyrolysis of ceramic coatings was carried out in the air at the temperature of 850 °C for 1 hour. This study describes the development of the oxidation resistant environmental barrier coatings on ferritic stainless steel grade AISI 441 and the oxidation behaviour of steel substrates and prepared PDC coatings. The selected samples of the composite layers were tested from the point of view of their oxidative resistance in the atmosphere of air at temperatures up to 1000 °C and different exposures time ranging from 1 to 96 hours. The purpose of the oxidation tests is a detailed microstructural analysis of the oxide layer formed on samples with selected types of PDC coatings in a synthetic air atmosphere at different temperatures and exposure times, while non-coated steel (AISI 441) was used as a reference material. The rate of oxidation in flow-through air atmosphere was determined, and detailed microstructural and phase analysis of the oxide scales formed on coated and uncoated samples after different exposures times and temperatures was performed by SEM/EDS and XRD. X-ray diffraction confirmed extensive oxidation of the uncoated AISI441 stainless steel accompanied by formation of a Cr₂O₃, TiO₂ and a (Mn, Cr)₃O₄ spinel containing layer of oxidation products. Beneficial effect of the PDC coatings was observed, demonstrated by marked reduction of the weight gain of coated steel after exposure to flowing air.